

Tools for the socio-economic context and SWOT analyses of the CAP Strategic Plans

OBJECTIVES AND CHALLENGES

Member States are required by Reg. 2115/2021 (Art. 115) to underpin the preparation of their CAP strategic plans with SWOT analyses of the socio-economic context for each specific CAP objective based on **common context indicators and other quantitative and qualitative up-to-date information**. For this task, most Member States have combined the (statistical) analysis of quantitative indicators with the consultation of stakeholders. The task can be challenging in that it needs to **reflect the heterogeneity across the entire national territory** (especially when there are relevant regional differences), include lessons learned from the past programming period, and properly use stakeholders' perspectives to complement the analysis of quantitative indicators.

MAIN TOOLS ADOPTED: STRENGTHS AND WEAKNESSES

World Café (DE, FI)

The world café method is a structured conversational process for **knowledge sharing** in which small groups of people discuss a topic at several small tables (like in a café). A world café can be made up of several thematic workshops, shedding light on different topics. The workshops start with short presentations related to the topic, which are followed by group discussions and idea collection (e.g. on whiteboard papers). Each group has a host that poses the questions/issues to be answered/debated and notes down the answers. At the end of each round, the participants (except for the hosts) are reshuffled into new groups, starting a new round of conversation. The host shares the insights from the previous groups with the new one. It ends with all hosts sharing the main takeaways for a joint discussion. This tool is usually used to **identify strengths, weaknesses, and development needs** related to different topics in a participatory and engaging way.

It allows the involvement of a broad range of diverse stakeholders, help cross-pollinate ideas and build upon each other's contributions, and explore complex topics from multiple perspectives in a structured way.

It requires the involvement of a large group of participants and intense facilitation to feed the discussion, whereas the output can tend to over-summarise the collected ideas.

Consultation forums (SE)

Consultative forums are a way to work with stakeholders, aiming to collect a wide range of views on various aspects of the strategic plans. They are used to acquire knowledge and perspectives from stakeholders on specific matters, to **increase the quality of decisions** made by strengthening dialogue, making use of expertise, collecting a broader range of perspectives, and increasing the number of involved stakeholders. The forums cover topics such as **general strategy, SWOT analysis, needs assessment, and draft interventions**. Most forums are conducted online, with participants given options to comment by speaking, writing, or sending remarks within a given time frame. This tool aims to **collect a wide range of views** on various aspects of the CAP reform.

It allows for reaching a broad range of stakeholders in a cost-effective way at multiple stages of the plans' design process, in order to disseminate draft outputs from the preparation of the plans and gather a feedback.

Limited clarity in the selection process and lack of a co-creative approach. It is mostly a top-down, one-way feedback mechanism with limited potential to generate consensus or agreement over complex issues.

MAPP (Programmes Impact Assessment Method) (DE)

This participatory tool, based on regional workshops and qualitative analysis techniques, was used to **assess the overall contributions of the Rural Development Programmes (RDP)**. The tool, which was also recommended by European Commission guidelines and the European Evaluation Helpdesk, allows to put the program impact in relation to policy instruments and measures outside of the RDP, and to assess environmental impacts. The tool relies on a trend analysis and on the creation of an **impact matrix to assess and visualise the relations between instruments, group of instruments, and impacts**.

It can look beyond the RDP by assessing other programmes. The used scoring system, while experimental, provide useful impacts' visualisations.

The preparation can be time-consuming, and it was challenging to cover all instruments in one workshop. Impacts' mechanisms cannot be taken into account. It may need re-adaptation.

Find more insights in the Inventory of tools online